

Paper 1

**THE PROBLEMS AND CHALLENGES OF THE HANDLOOM INDUSTRY–
A CASE STUDY OF CHENDAMANGALAM, ERNAKULAM (DT.)
KERALA.**

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ABSTRACT

Handloom is the most widely recognized cottage industry of Kerala that is widespread throughout the rural areas. It employs a large skilled and unskilled workforce and which, in chendamangalam society, mainly consists of women workers, handloom spinning and weaving were the main occupations. The objective of this paper is to assess the female work participation in the handloom industry of Chendamangalam. The study focuses to analyse the socio-economic condition of the weavers, derived from primary data collected through interview schedules of 35 active members of chendamangalam society. Results show that weaving is the major occupation of Chendamangalam, as there is a high concentration of handlooms. The major reasons which forced females to do work in handlooms are an economic necessity, unemployment, low income, low literacy, and education.

Keywords: Handloom industry, Work participation, Female weavers, chendamangalam handloom society.

Introduction

The handloom industry in India has a very long history spanning over centuries. Handloom spinning and weaving were the main occupations of the people in rural areas. Unfortunately, this industry has been declining owing to so many reasons. This sector contributes nearly 15% of the cloth production in the country and also contributes to the export earnings of the country. Handloom weaving is one of the largest economic activities after agriculture providing direct and indirect employment to 35.23 lakh weavers and allied workers. It employs more than 1.5 lakh people in Kerala. (Annual Report Ministry of Textile 2020-21 August). In Kerala, hand weaving was a traditional occupation of Chalayan's, the main weaving caste. This industry is mainly concentrated in Kannur, Kozhikode, Ernakulam, and Trivandrum districts. At present, this industry is facing a severe crisis due to increased cost of production, marketing difficulties, and working

capital problems. Handloom always promotes innovations in its products through experimentation and exhibitions. The strength of handloom lies in introducing innovative designs, which cannot be replicated by the power loom sector. Thus, handloom forms a part of the heritage of Kerala and represents the richness and diversity of the state and the creativity of the weavers. As most of the weaver societies were situated in a rural areas, it has a major role in improving the livelihood of rural people as well as eradicating poverty in the area.

Handloom industries are producing eco-friendly and energy-saving products, resulting in the enhancement of sustainable development. Kerala’s handloom products are well applauded for their attractive designs, elegant craftsmanship, exciting colors, and delicate texture. For centuries, the majority of the product had been made by family weavers and each with a unique story on how they were introduced to this special trade. The dexterity of the weavers of Chendamangalam in Ernakulam district is very famous across the world. There are five handloom weavers’ co-operative societies functioning in Paravoor. Each society has its handloom units, founded in 1954, the business name Chendamangalam handloom society runs under the brand name Chendamangalam handloom which is owned by Griesh Kumar located in Paravoor, Kochi, is one of the oldest in the locality. Society has 235 weavers. The workforce is predominantly female, constituting 91 percent of the total workforce. The yarn, thread, and dye solutions are provided by various handloom weavers co-operative societies. Weavers work at home and provide a finished product to these societies.

Women contributed substantially to the economic prosperity of the nation. The handloom sector is the only manufacturing sector wherein one finds a large number of women producing products that are worn by a large number of women. A unique feature of the chendamangalam handloom sector is that 91per cent of women produces almost 60 percent of women products. At present, the Handloom industry is declining which has directly affected the women workers of this industry. Their work participation has increased as well as the increase in per day working hours has resultant more health issues especially about physical problems. The present study has highlighted the work participation and socio-economic condition of weavers of Chendamangalam handloom society.

Objectives

- To analyze the socio-economic conditions of female weavers in Chendamangalam handloom society, Ernakulam (Dt.)
- To identify the nature of problems of the female employees.
- To analyze women’s participation and involvement in the weaving occupation.

Scope and profile of the study area

Chendamangalam is a small town and a panchayat in Paravoor Taluk Ernakulam district in the state of Kerala, India. It belongs to the Central Kerala Division. It is located 30 km towards north from district headquarters Kakkannad,3km from Paravoor,237 km from state capital Thiruvandapuram. It is spread over an area of 10.83 km². This town comprises 18 wards (Local self-government report of Kerala.) As of the 2021 India census, Chendamangalam had a population of 28,133. Males

constitute 48% of the population and females 52%.

It is famous for handloom. The weaving products are famous in the brand name of “chendamangalam kaithari”. The weaving products are Kerala cotton saree, women’s set mundu, cotton dupatta, men’s dhoti, and shirting fabrics. This weaving tradition was set up by the Devangana Chettiar community who were resided at Chendamangalam in the 16th century for the Paliath Achan family, the hereditary Prime minister of the Kingdom of Cochin. They started by weaving fine Muslim dhotis. The handloom tradition flourished into sarees and other fabrics under the aristocrats of Cochin. The weaving waned by the early 20th century as a result of diminishing patronage. However, through the Chendamangalam Handloom Co-operative Society formed in 1954 and The Kerala Co-operative Society Act of 1969, the handloom witnessed a revival.

Methodology

The present study is intended to adopt the Descriptive Research design, based on both the primary and secondary sources of data. The primary data is collected with the help of a direct interview with the respondent to collect information about the socio-economic conditions of the female weavers in Chendamangalam taluk. Chendamangalam taluk has 376 handloom weavers out of which 35 female weavers from Kuriappilly handloom weaver’s co-operative society have been selected for interview. Care was also taken in the selection of handloom households that should be truly representative of their wards. After the collection of data, data were converted into tabular form. After analyzing these tables inferences have been made about the various socio-economic conditions of female weavers of the study area. The study limits itself to women weaver’s issues and focuses on suggesting solutions to solve their problems.

Review of Literature

Dr. Dharam Chand Jain, Miss Ritu Gera (2017) conducted AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF the HANDLOOM INDUSTRY OF INDIA. Their study outlines the handloom industry and the difficulties related to production and manufacturing units. They think that weavers should be well informed about the schemes so that they can gain benefits from the government and various social, co-operative agencies. They also suggest that proper training and tutoring about the new technologies of production should be provided to the employees.

Dr. Selvaraj A and Tamilrasi N (2016) studied FACTORS INFLUENCING HANDLOOM WEAVERS TO ENTER INTO THE FIELD. Their main objectives were to measure the factors influencing the handloom weavers to enter into the field and to offer suitable suggestions for further development. In this study, a lot of factors are found to enter into this field that as heredity, easy to start, less working capital, practical knowledge, availability of raw materials, etc. Out of this earning of regular income is the most important factor to enter into the handloom field.

Dr. Manoj P K and Rajesh S (2013) have studied the quality of work-life (QWL) and other variables relating to industrial relations scenarios in textile units in the Kannur district of North Kerala. Suggestions for improving the QWL are made based on the findings of the study

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Dr. Manoj P K and Rajesh S (2015) have studied the work-life of women workers and their job satisfaction has been studied, concerning textile units in the Malabar region (Northern part) of Kerala. Accordingly, 300 workers in various units in the unorganized sector were studied. Kannur district of North Kerala. Issues relating to social security, legal protection, etc. of women workers of textile units were covered in this study. Suggestions for improving the QWL are made based on the findings of the study.

Ajithan (2006) in his study found that there are good prospects for the handloom industry in Kerala during the post-globalization period, which is evident in the increase in handloom export from Kerala during that period

Selvaraj (2007) stated that due to outdated technology and competition from mills and power looms, the handloom sector is experiencing continuous loss. The management of the societies is not sound, and the financial and operational efficiency is poor.

Suresh Kumar (2008) found that the handloom co-operatives in Kerala are on the verge of a crisis in terms of economic indicators such as production, marketing, and finance and depend deeply on the budgetary support of the government for their survival.

Sivagnanasithi (2008) in his study found that health problems, low and irregular wages, shortage and lack of supply of raw materials, low status in the society, etc are the major problems faced by the members of the co-operative society. The co-operative societies are facing problems like poor marketing facilities, poor performance, and low income.

Result of the Study

Table-1 Age of the female weavers

Sl. No.	age	frequency	percentage
1	30-40	1	03
2	40-50	3	09
3	50-60	19	54
4	60 and above	12	34
	Total	35	100

The age of the respondents: out of the respondents, 03 percent respondents belong to the age group of 30 to 40 years, 09 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 40-50 years, following 54 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 50 to 60 years and remaining, 34 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 60 and above years.

Table-2 Educational status of the female weavers

Sl. No.		frequency	percentage
1	Upper primary	24	68
2	High school	9	26
3	Higher secondary	2	6
	Total	35	100

The educational status of weaving women: It is very evident that only less educated persons engaged in this work. They have no other optional work to do and it is only unavoidable to them. The majority of the respondents i.e., 68 percent having upper primary education and 26 percent have secondary level education and the sad thing is that only a less percent of the respondent i.e., 06 percent of them have higher secondary Level education.

Table -3 Family size of the female weavers

Sl. No.	members	frequency	percentage
1	1-4	19	54
2	4-7	16	46
	Total	35	100

Family size of the weavers: Out of the respondents 54 percent of weaving women are from a family of a maximum of four members and about 46 percent of weaving women are living in a family of a maximum of seven members. All the respondents are from the nuclear family.

Table- 4 loom ownership

Sl. No.	Number of looms	frequency	percentage
1	No loom	8	23
2	One loom	27	77
	total	35	100

The numbers of looms had by weavers: During the field visit, most of the houses i.e., 77 percent I went to had only one loom, and these looms were provided by the co-operative societies themselves. Out of respondents, 23per cent of the weavers has no looms. They weave in the looms which were owned and operated by the co-operative society.

Table- 5 categories of weavers

Sl. No.	Categories of weavers	frequency	percentage
1	independent	-	
2	Dependant (weaves for co-operative)	35	100

As this case study shows, the role of the weavers’ co-operative has been significant. From the study, it is clear that all the weavers are weaving for a cooperative society. However, the co-operative has been unable to provide continuous work, weavers are pushed into depending on the co-operative society for their livelihood.

Table- 6 occupational background of weavers

Sl. No.		frequency	percentage
1	hereditary	31	89
2	Non-hereditary	4	11
	Total	35	100

The respondent’s opinion on the reason for opting for the weaving occupation: The majority of the respondents i.e., 89 percent, expressed their occupation by hereditary. Following, nearly one-tenth of the respondents i.e., 20 percent, expressed their occupation as non-hereditary. Some of them opined that they have other job ideas along with this occupation and the remaining respondents have expressed that they selected this profession because of the easiness and convenience to do. Therefore, a greater number of people involved few of the people engaged in weaving work due to the nature of work being easy and affordable.

Table- 7 salary of the weavers

Sl. No.	salary	frequency	percentage
1	3000-4000	11	31
2	4000-5000	14	40
3	5000-6000	10	29
	Total	35	100

The data shows that 31 percent of the respondents are paid the minimum salary of 3000 -4000 rupees.40 percent of the weavers are paid 4000-5000 rupees and 29 percent of the weavers are

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having a maximum of 6000 rupees. The weavers are getting only meager income so that many workers are moving out from the Chendamangalam handloom industry thus they are not able to survive. However, if it is ensuring a permanent minimum wage, the workers are willing to stay there.

Table- 8 satisfaction of the weavers

Sl. No.		frequency	percentage
1	satisfied	6	17
2	dissatisfied	19	54
3	Extremely dissatisfied	10	29
	total	35	100

The respondent’s opinion on the satisfaction of the income of weaving: only 17 percent of the weavers have expressed that they do not satisfy with the income incurred by weaving. 54 percent, have expressed that they are dissatisfied with their income and 29 percent of the weavers have expressed that they are extremely dissatisfied with their income.

Table- 9 working experience of the weavers

Sl. No.	Working experience (years)	frequency	percentage
1	1-4	1	3
2	4-8	3	9
3	8-12	4	12
4	12-16	12	35
5	16 and above	15	44
	total	35	100

This case study shows that the majority of the respondents are having more than 16 years of experience. Out of the respondents, 35 percent of the weavers have 12-16 years of experience and 12 percent of the weavers have 8-12 years of experience. Only for a very small percentage of workers ie,3 percent of weavers are had 1-4 years of experience. From this study, we can understand very clearly that all the weavers are highly experienced and skilled. And this study also indicates that young generations are changing their interest in weaving from handloom to other employment potential areas.

Table- 10 health problems faced by the weavers

Sl. No	Health problems	frequency	percentage
1	Low vision and back pain	3	9
2	Low vision and leg pain	6	16
3	Low vision, leg pain, and back pain	26	75
	total	35	100

The opinion on the problems of the weaver facing: the majority of the respondents i.e., 75 percent, expressed that they are suffering from low vision, leg pain, and back pain. The majority of the workers are aged weavers and so they are suffering from old age problems and they opined that they have physically and mentally stressed.

Conclusion

The handloom industry is one of the ancient traditional occupations in Kerala. Chendamangalam is famous throughout the world for one thing the centuries-long heritage of the handloom industry. It all started hundreds of years before in “Paliyam Palace”. The Chendamangalam handloom industry was a symbol of pride for the “Paliyath Achan “family. It has a reputed name. Some years back there was a very good demand for the product, lately, there is flooding in the market with new cloth material type like polyester. This leads to a gradual decline in the handloom industry and has badly affected the income of weavers. The above study brings out the fact that female weavers of Chendamangalam are very poor from an economic point of view. Weavers are getting merger income from weaving, earning does not sufficient for maintaining of the family, and, fulfilment of family needs. As a result, they had begun to search for a better opportunity. The continuous decline of the handloom industry has increased the health problems in female weavers as their work is more physical. The status of education and health facilities is also very poor. Only with the full support and co-operation of the government, this working class will be able to sustain itself in this sector. So, a greater number of policies, programs, and education of the working women in the weaving industry.

SUGGESTIONS

- Government should encourage the government-owned enterprises to purchase handloom products. It should insist on government employees wearing such garments at least once every week to boost the demand for such products.
- The pending disbursements (like subsidies, rebates, etc.) to weavers and other workers in this industry need to be fully paid so as to motivate them to put in their full potential.

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- Cost competitiveness of this industry segment, at present, is very poor. This in turn affects the profit margins and sales of the product. Stricter measures to control cost through adoption of advanced technologies, engagement of trained and skilled staff, etc.
- Specialized training needs to be given to the handloom employees for the meaningful marketing of handloom products through cost-effective distribution channels

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